

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL DETERMINANTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGEMENT SKILLS IN LEADERS OF GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *This article talks about the socio-psychological determinants of management skills development in the management staff of general secondary education organizations.*

Keywords: *management personnel, management skills, management activity, level of competence, leadership creativity, educational system, social relations, tasks of management, functional approach, foreign experiences.*

A leader with a high level of competence and his strategic management creates an opportunity to implement innovative programs that determine the high level of creativity of the leader and ensure the development of the organization. For this reason, improving the social and psychological conditions of the management of the general secondary education system based on the development of the social and psychological competence of the leader is an important psychological problem.

The tasks of management are to teach the leaders of the general education system in-depth theoretical and practical knowledge of the socio-psychological origin and necessity of the management process, management styles, management functions and categories, object-subject relations in management, the main principles and laws of management.

The main goals of developing the communication culture and social-psychological competence of school principals simultaneously include the following scientific basis from both the theoretical and practical sides:

- further improvement of the system of training mature leaders who can think creatively;
- formation of a modern leader with socio-psychological competence;
- development of recommendations aimed at developing a leader with a high communication culture and a modern image;
- improvement of a leader who can educate and raise a generation that is spiritually healthy, intellectually mature, and mentally harmonious;

Achieving the training of cognitive and initiative leaders who can create a base of necessary opportunities for the pedagogical team.

In solving the tasks in this regard, the current state of the national education system is to modernize it based on the requirements of the times, prepare young people for management from the pedagogical and psychological side, educate them as physically and spiritually healthy people as possessors of high knowledge and enlightenment, It is the need of the hour to increase the authority of the leaders and pedagogues of educational institutions, to make effective use of the available opportunities for their effective activity, and to implement consistent measures to create the necessary conditions for the management of the general education system.

If we look at the history of human development, the development of any country or society has been directly dependent on the attention paid to the education system and quality personnel management. As a result of relying on such methodological connections, the management process has achieved a socio-psychologically active rise. In addition to the fundamental reform of the general secondary education system, which is the foundation of the personnel training system, special attention is being paid to improving the social and psychological competence of school principals. Also, material support for principals of general secondary schools, systematic improvement of their qualifications, proper organization of pedagogical activities of general education school staff, further increase of the status and prestige of pedagogical staff in society, Many laws and programs have been developed in order to improve the lifestyle of teachers and teachers, create the necessary conditions for their conscious activity and free creativity, and effective work is being carried out in this regard.

Competence is the ability to apply the theoretical knowledge acquired in a specific direction or specialty, acquired skills, and acquired skills in solving practical and theoretical issues encountered in everyday life.

No matter what profession a person has, if he approaches his work and training diligently and lovingly, he will perfectly master its secrets, at the same time, he will realize himself and find perfection in this field. That's why the school director loves his team and children and educates them, they will grow up well.

The psychology of the leader - when analyzing the employee's performance, focuses on the management process and whether it is suitable or not for the subordinate's needs or abilities, according to which individual personal characteristics he was promoted to the level of the boss, what methods of management he uses to successfully carry out the work, to the employees focuses on a number of issues such as what methods of influence he uses in order to have a psychological effect.

To date, the main goal of the implementation of new approaches, active reforms, modern methods, methods and tools in the education system is the training of fully mature specialist leaders and their personality formation in the spirit of national and universal values.

Based on the socio-psychological nature of this process, a person capable of developing a democratic and legal state and civil society, capable of personal position, active social character, high management ability, cognitively and creatively level, self-discipline in any situation It is aimed at preparing leading personnel who can manage, sincere, organize the management process in a fair way, who are proactive, thoughtful and can contribute to the interests of the state and society using modern methods and tools and create their reserves.

It is known that the management of the general secondary education system is considered a complex process and requires creative approaches, intellectual potential, and cognitive skills from the leader. Because a single error and shortcoming in the educational process has a negative impact on the system of social relations, the interests of the state and society.

Judging from the above, the success of a person's efforts to satisfy his needs evokes positive emotions, and his encounter with difficulties and defeat evokes negative emotions.

Positive feelings and negative feelings can be divided into two groups. They are:

Stenic emotions are a positive emotional state that arouses enthusiasm in a person and causes courage: strong joy, strong anger, fighting spirit, bravery, etc.

Asthenic emotions - an emotional state that reduces the vital activity of a person, weakens his enthusiasm: sadness, despair, indifference, sadness, etc.

Society is a set of social relations formed at a certain stage of human historical development. A person is considered as a conscious being. Therefore, at the same time, he is both the manager and the managed, as well as a direct participant in social relations. Also, a person is a member of society.

At this point, it should be noted that realization of the concept of personality in society, education and training of youth existed in all periods of human development. If the parents are the cause of the child's birth and physical formation, then their preparation for life, personal development, career guidance, and future service to the society and the state will be formed directly on the basis of the skills and work of the teachers. All of this depends on the correct approach to social relations and effective management of the educational system. Because any work requires people to get along with each other, to transfer various information to each other, and to exchange ideas.

Often in everyday communication, we often use the concepts of "competence" or "knowledge". In the 90s of the 20th century, the International Labor Organization, which sets qualification requirements for specialists, introduced the concept of "basic competencies" in professional retraining of management personnel. "Competence" is a Latin word whose dictionary meaning in Uzbek means "a person who knows well", "having experience". In everyday life, attention is often paid to the concept of social and psychological competence.

Today, the success of the work depends to a large extent on the management skills and positive psychological competence of the heads of educational institutions. It is important for managers to know their subordinates from a scientific and practical point of view in assessing their personal qualities, usefulness and many other worthy aspects, having studied their subordinates objectively and comprehensively, skillful, positive psychological characteristics.

Today, as a result of the fundamental reform of the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the acceleration of the process of implementation in accordance with the requirements of the time depends in many ways on the contributions of the heads of educational institutions and the correct organization of leadership activities. Therefore, in the current period of social development, educational institutions are not leaders who blindly perform tasks in the instructions and directive documents of higher organizations, but creative approaches to their activities and every work, modern, pedagogy, psychology with new thinking, , who is aware of management sciences and can skillfully use them, as well as has excellent personal qualities, unique characteristics, management skills, a certain culture of behavior, faith, ideological and political knowledge, appearance, feelings it is necessary to appoint employees who can understand feelings, traditions, customs, dedication, determination, literacy, social activity, organization and entrepreneurship. Leadership is not a set of different tasks or a course of action, but a high-level expression of the ability to manage others. Therefore, to lead, a person needs the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications, skills, professional sophistication, experience, abilities and unique characteristics.

Leadership:

- great art;
- professional activity with special content;
- creative activity aimed at improving the activity;

● is pedagogical management. In fact, because management is a joint activity with people and communication between them, all the actions of the leader and the team, the creation of favorable and necessary conditions for the activity of the educational institution, the relationship between the teacher and the students focuses on creating a friendly psychological environment and creative activity. This means that the leader can study the employees, select them for the educational institution, educational process, assign them to positions and tasks based on their abilities and knowledge levels, demand the strict execution of important instructions and orders. It requires professional abilities and skills such as being able to notice their unique virtues, achievements and shortcomings, being able to use their achievements, eliminating their shortcomings, and being able to use the opportunities of employees widely.

Therefore, special importance is attached to the issue of organizing the process of selecting leaders for the management system, and in most cases, leaders are selected based on the following criteria:

1. Spiritual-educational and political maturity. The ability of the future leader to correctly understand and interpret state policy, to be able to organize the activities of the institution based on current directions.

2. Having the necessary experience, knowledge, skills and qualifications for a leadership position, as well as knowledge of management principles, analysis, planning, and all aspects of the position held.

3. To be able to properly direct, organize, diagnose, predict and plan the activities of the employees of the institution.

4. Morality and upbringing, reputation, honesty, fairness, simplicity and modesty, high demands on oneself and others, high sense of responsibility and dedication to one's duties and responsibilities being highly developed and intolerant of all shortcomings.

5. Unity of work with words - diligence and perseverance, the ability to influence the timely and independent implementation of decisions received from state bodies and adopted by the institution.

6. Knowledge of management psychology - the ability to form a goal-oriented, comprehensively developed team with scientific and creative potential and to create an acceptable social and psychological environment.

7. To be able to correctly distribute the duties of the deputy heads, heads of departments and employees of the institution and to evaluate their work objectively.

8. To be able to properly organize one's labor activities, to be able to divide them into levels in terms of their importance, based on the volume of work to be performed. Being able to create an opportunity for moderation in the team of the institution and the effectiveness of the work process based on proper planning of their activities.

Based on the above-mentioned criteria, the following directions specific to management were developed:

1. The administration should be formed in a national and universal character, should be compatible with social and psychological norms and should have a modern appearance.

2. Such as having a critical attitude to one's own activities, developing self-control and management-specific social-psychological competence.

3. Conscious operation of modern management and having a creative approach characteristic of a leader.

4. A leader should have self-control skills and know how to critically analyze his work. Based on the above analysis, we can conclude that the socio-psychological competence characteristic of management is such a direction of the leader and his general culture that, in addition to the knowledge that applies only to him, the result of this knowledge It also requires knowledge of the psychological processes and situations that ensure the improvement of the ways and skills.

The following recommendations were developed in order to further improve the socio-psychological competence of the leaders of the educational system and to highlight the scientific and practical significance of the research:

1. Regular systematic analysis of the activities of the heads of the general education system based on foreign experiences and increasing their effectiveness.

2. Development of popular proposals and recommendations for ensuring gender equality and sexual equality of leaders, more precisely: equality between men and women.

3. Stimulating the activities of the leaders of the active educational system in the region.

4. Comparative analysis of the activities of directors of secondary schools in remote districts and villages with the management of educational institutions in urban centers and their equalization.

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